

Synthesis of novel 1,2,3-triazole incorporated quinoline derivatives *via* click chemistry and evaluation of their antimalarial activity[†]

Ritu Mamgain^a, Himanshu Atheaya^a, Shabana I. Khan^b, Sunny Manohar^a and Diwan S. Rawat^{*a}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, University of Delhi, Delhi-110 007, India

E-mail : dsrawat@chemistry.du.ac.in *Fax* : 91-11-27667501

^bNational Centre for Natural Products Research, University of Mississippi, Oxford, MS 38677, USA

Manuscript received 05 January 2014, accepted 15 January 2014

Abstract : A series of structurally diverse novel 1,2,3-triazole incorporated quinoline derivatives (7a-g and 8a-l) were prepared *via* simple and efficient click chemistry involving Cu^I catalyzed intermolecular Huisgen [3+2] cycloaddition reaction in good to excellent yields. All the synthesized compounds were evaluated for their antimalarial activity against CQ-sensitive (D6 clone) and CQ-resistant (W2-clone) strains of *P. falciparum* and mammalian cell cytotoxicity against Vero cells in an *in vitro* assay.

Keywords : Quinoline, click chemistry, 1,2,3-triazoles, antimalarial activity.

Introduction

Click chemistry has played a vital role in all aspects of drug discovery including pharmaceutical polymers¹, bioconjugation strategies for proteomics², lead optimization through combinatorial screenings² and generation of natural product derivatives³. The term 'click' refers to reliable, facile, efficient, selective and versatile chemical transformations, which lead to a single reaction product and uses readily available insensitive starting materials. Among the many known click reactions, Cu^I catalyzed intermolecular Huisgen [3+2] cycloaddition⁴ between a terminal alkyne and an azide to generate substituted 1,2,3-triazoles is of great interest as it has found tremendous applications in various facets of drug development programme. This ligation process by which two entities are linked through formation of 1,2,3-triazoles came out like a dream for medicinal chemists all over the world². The formation of triazole is especially relevant for drug discovery as it has favorable physicochemical properties². Triazoles serve as rigid linking units that are almost impossible to oxidize or reduce, cannot be easily cleaved hydrolytically and nitrogen atoms at position 2 and 3

functions as weak hydrogen bond acceptors. Chimeric drugs bearing two distinct activities like linezolid-macrolide (1)⁵ and vancomycin-cephalosporin (2)⁶ conjugates have been synthesised successfully by this approach (Fig. 1).

Quinoline based drugs like chloroquine (CQ; 3)⁷ and amodiaquine (4)⁸ were long been used as an effective antimalarial therapeutics in malarial chemotherapy. However in the past few decades, their efficacy declined drastically due to the ever increasing drug-resistant problems⁹. Researchers have found that if the quinoline moiety is connected to other antimalarial entities *via* systematic chemical modifications, it can improve antimalarial activity against *Plasmodium falciparum* resistant strains⁹. It may be noted that, *Plasmodium falciparum* is the most virulent of the five *Plasmodium* species that causes human malaria and is responsible for most of the malarial related deaths^{10,11}. Previous reports from our lab showed that when quinoline moiety is connected to triazole moiety *via* different alkyl chain linker to get 4-aminoquinoline-triazole (5) and 4-aminoquinoline-triazole-triazine (6) based hybrids (Fig. 1), it exhibited promising antimalarial ac-

[†]In honour of Professor K. C. Joshi on the occasion of his 88th birthday.

Fig. 1. Chimeric drugs incorporating 1,2,3-triazoles synthesized via click chemistry.

tivity against both CQ-sensitive (D6 clone; IC_{50} ranging from 0.58 to 7.24 μM) and CQ-resistant (W2 clone; IC_{50} ranging from 0.73 to 11.52 μM) strains of *P. falciparum* without any cytotoxicity towards mammalian (Vero) cells when tested *in vitro*¹². Encouraged by these results and in continuation of our work of developing medically relevant scaffolds¹²⁻¹⁹, in the present investigation, we modified these hybrids by connecting the triazole moiety directly to quinoline entity (7a-g and 8a-l) *via* azide-alkyne click chemistry in an anticipation that these hybrids may

show better antimalarial activity.

Results and discussion

As Cu^I catalyzed intermolecular Huisgen [3+2] cycloaddition reaction needs alkyne and azide counterparts for the generation of 1,2,3-triazole ring. For the alkyne counterpart, either commercially available alkynes were taken or they were prepared by modified literature methods using various substituted phenols (9a-l) and treating them with propargyl bromide in the presence of anhy-

Fig. 2. Chloroquine (CQ), 3; Amodiaquine (AQ), 4; General structure of 4-aminoquinoline-triazole hybrids, 5 and 4-aminoquinoline-triazole-triazole hybrids, 6 synthesized previously in our lab; General structure of 1,2,3-triazole incorporated quinoline derivatives synthesized in present investigation, 7a-g and 8a-l.

Mamgain *et al.* : Synthesis of novel 1,2,3-triazole incorporated quinoline derivatives *via* click chemistry *etc.*

drous K_2CO_3 in dry DMF at 80 °C for 2–3 h to yield corresponding aromatic ring substituted alkynes **10a-l** (Scheme 1).

9a ; R = H	10a ; R = H
9b ; R = <i>o</i> -CH ₃	10b ; R = <i>o</i> -CH ₃
9c ; R = <i>m</i> -CH ₃	10c ; R = <i>m</i> -CH ₃
9d ; R = <i>p</i> -CH ₃	10d ; R = <i>p</i> -CH ₃
9e ; R = <i>p</i> -Cl	10e ; R = <i>p</i> -Cl
9f ; R = <i>o,p</i> -di-Cl	10f ; R = <i>o,p</i> -di-Cl
9g ; R = 2,6-di-Cl	10g ; R = 2,6-di-Cl
9h ; R = <i>o</i> -NO ₂	10h ; R = <i>o</i> -NO ₂
9i ; R = <i>p</i> -NO ₂	10i ; R = <i>p</i> -NO ₂
9j ; R = <i>o</i> -NO ₂ , <i>p</i> -CH ₃	10j ; R = <i>o</i> -NO ₂ , <i>p</i> -CH ₃
9k ; R = <i>o</i> -CHO	10k ; R = <i>o</i> -CHO
9l ; R = <i>p</i> -CHO	10l ; R = <i>p</i> -CHO

Scheme 1. (a) K_2CO_3 , DMF, 80 °C, 2–3 h, 75–90%.

The azide counterpart was synthesized by treating 4,7-dichloroquinoline (**11**) with sodium azide in DMF as a solvent at 60 °C as depicted in Scheme 2. In the final step, the azide substituted quinoline (**12**) was subjected to click reactions with alkynes in the presence of sodium ascorbate and $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$ in *t*-BuOH/ H_2O (1 : 1), leading to the formation of desired hybrid molecules (**7a-g**

and **8a-l**; Table 1) in good to excellent yield (Scheme 2). All of the reported compounds (**7a-g** and **8a-l**) were purified over silica gel column and characterized spectroscopically.

Table 1. Synthesised 1,2,3-triazole incorporated quinoline derivatives with their melting points and observed yield

Compound	R	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)
7a	CH ₂ OH	147–149	88
7b	CH ₂ CH ₂ OH	163–165	85
7c	C(CH ₃) ₂ OH	167–169	82
7d	C ₆ H ₅	153–155	78
7e	CH ₂ Br	141–143	75
7f	CH ₂ OCH ₃	83–85	73
7g	Cyclohexanol-1	151–153	75
8a	H	97–99	85
8b	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	93–95	83
8c	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	109–111	85
8d	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	105–107	85
8e	<i>p</i> -Cl	144–146	80
8f	<i>o,p</i> -di-Cl	188–190	82
8g	2,6-di-Cl	250–252	85
8h	<i>o</i> -NO ₂	194–196	78
8i	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	229–231	80
8j	<i>o</i> -NO ₂ , <i>p</i> -CH ₃	179–181	86
8k	<i>o</i> -CHO	209–211	70
8l	<i>p</i> -CHO	169–171	75

Scheme 2. (a) NaN_3 , DMF, 60 °C, 3 h, 70%; (b) $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$, sodium ascorbate, *t*-butanol : H_2O (1 : 1), 45 °C, 6 h, 70–80%.

The *in vitro* antimalarial activity of all the synthesised 1,2,3-triazole incorporated quinoline derivatives (**7a-g** and **8a-l**) were evaluated against both CQ-sensitive (D6 clone) and CQ-resistant (W2 clone) strains of *P. falciparum* using CQ as a standard drug, while mammalian cell cytotoxicity was determined against Vero cells using doxorubicin as the standard. Surprisingly, screening results revealed that none of the test compounds showed any significant activity up to the highest tested concentration of 48 μM . When we compared these results with our previous published result¹², we found that the presence of alkyl chain linker connecting quinoline moiety with 1,2,3-triazole entity is very important for imparting antimalarial activity. The alkyl chain brings flexibility to the otherwise rigid molecule which can help in binding efficiently to the receptor sites within biological system. All the compounds, however, were found to be non-toxic towards mammalian (Vero) cells proving their safe toxicity profile.

Conclusion

In summary, a structurally diverse series of nineteen 1,2,3-triazole incorporated quinoline derivatives were prepared *via* simple and efficient azide-alkyne click chemistry in good to excellent yields. All the compounds were tested for their antimalarial activity against CQ-sensitive (D6 clone) and CQ-resistant (W2-clone) strains of *P. falciparum* and mammalian cell cytotoxicity against Vero cells in an *in vitro* assay. Although, none of the compounds showed any significant antimalarial activity up to the highest tested concentration of 48 μM but they were found to be non cytotoxic up to highest tested concentrations indicating their safety in the mammalian system. The diminished antimalarial activity can be attributed to the absence of linear alkyl chain linker which can bring flexibility in the molecule. So, at the end it can be concluded that, this study provided significant insights towards the structure activity relationship studies (SAR) of quinoline based hybrid antimalarial agents which could be beneficial for further modification in structural framework. Further investigation is under progress, and results will be published in due course of time.

Experimental

All of the chemicals used in the synthesis were pur-

chased from Sigma-Aldrich and were used as such. Thin layer chromatography was used to monitor the progress of the reactions. All of the compounds were purified over silica gel column. Solvents were distilled before using for purification purposes. Melting points were determined on ERS automated melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. IR (Film) and IR (KBr) spectra were recorded using Perkin-Elmer FT-IR spectrophotometer and the values are expressed as ν_{max} (cm^{-1}). The ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker Spectrospin spectrometer at 300 MHz and 75.5 MHz respectively using TMS as an internal standard. The chemical shift values are recorded on δ scale and the coupling constants (J) are in Hz. Mass spectral data were recorded on a Jeol (Japan) JMS-DX303 and micromass LCT, Mass spectrometer/Data system.

Synthesis and characterization of selected compounds :

General procedure for the synthesis of alkynes (10a-l) :

A solution of propargyl bromide (8.54 mmol) in dry DMF (10 mL) was added dropwise to a stirred suspension of substituted phenol (8.54 mmol) and anhydrous K_2CO_3 (42.70 mmol) in 10 mL of dry DMF at room temperature. The temperature was further increased to 80 °C and the progress of reaction was monitored by thin layer chromatography. After completion of reaction which takes about 2–3 h, the reaction mixture was poured into ice cold water (100 ml) and extracted with chloroform (3 \times 60 ml). The chloroform layer was dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and excess of solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The crude product thus obtained was purified over silica gel column using EtOAc/hexane as an eluent.

Procedure for the synthesis of 4-azido-7-chloroquinoline (12) :

A mixture of 4,7-dichloroquinoline (**11**, 10 g, 0.05 mol) and sodium azide (5.20 g, 0.08 mol) in dry DMF (100 mL) was heated at 60 °C. The progress of reaction was monitored by thin layer chromatography (TLC). Reaction took 3 h to complete. After completion, water (100 mL) was added to the reaction mixture and it was stirred additionally for 1 h. The solid separated was filtered, washed with excess of water and dried. The crude product thus obtained was purified over silica gel column using EtOAc/hexane as an eluent. Yield : 7.05 g (70%);

m.p. 117 °C; IR (Film, cm^{-1}) : 2122, 1609, 1565, 1491, 1419, 1372, 1352, 1305, 1278, 1203, 1144, 1071, 1009, 877, 839, 816, 765; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) : 7.48 (1H, d, J 5 Hz), 7.64 (1H, m), 8.00 (1H, d), 8.05 (1H, d), 8.86 (1H, d, J 5 Hz); Anal. calcd. for $\text{C}_9\text{H}_5\text{ClN}_4$: C, 52.82; H, 2.46; N, 27.43; found : C, 52.64; H, 2.29; N, 28.68.

General procedure for the synthesis of 1,2,3-triazole incorporated quinoline derivatives (7a-g) and (8a-l) :

To a stirred solution of compound **12** (1 mmol) and respected alkyne (1.1 mmol) in 10 mL *tert*-butyl alcohol, solution of $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.20 mmol) and sodium ascorbate (0.40 mmol) in distilled water (10 mL) was added. The deep yellow mixture was stirred vigorously at 45 °C and progress of reaction was monitored by thin layer chromatography. After 6 h, reaction was completed and crude reaction mixture was extracted with CHCl_3 (3 \times 20 mL). The combined organic layer was dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and excess of solvent was removed under vacuum. The crude material thus obtained was purified over SiO_2 column using EtOAc/hexane as an eluent.

1-[1-(7-Chloro-quinolin-4-yl)-1H-[1,2,3]triazol-4-yl]-methanol (7a) : IR (Film, cm^{-1}) : 3296, 3083, 2925, 1612, 1593, 1564, 1439, 1229, 1117, 1034, 880, 820; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : 2.64 (1H, brs, OH), 5.00 (2H, s, OCH_2), 7.50 (1H, d, J 3.6 Hz), 7.60 (1H, d, J 9.0 Hz), 7.97–8.04 (2H, m), 8.25 (1H, s), 9.07 (1H, d, J 3.6 Hz); HRMS calcd. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{ClN}_4\text{O}$: 260.0465; found : 261.4202 ($\text{M}^+ + \text{H}$).

2-[1-(7-Chloro-quinolin-4-yl)-1H-[1,2,3]triazol-4-yl]-ethanol (7b) : IR (Film, cm^{-1}) : 3392, 2951, 2928, 2881, 1613, 1567, 1506, 1456, 1439, 1229, 1117, 1050, 879, 820; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : 3.10 (2H, t, J 6 Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$), 3.97 (2H, s, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$), 4.40 (1H, brs, OH), 7.51–7.62 (2H, m), 8.08–8.11 (2H, m), 8.21 (1H, s), 9.06 (1H, d, J 4.5 Hz); Anal. calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{11}\text{ClN}_4\text{O}$: C, 56.84; H, 4.04; found : C: 56.64; H, 4.29.

2-[1-(7-Chloro-quinolin-4-yl)-1H-[1,2,3]triazol-4-yl]-propan-2-ol (7c) : IR (Film, cm^{-1}) : 3366, 2978, 2931, 1611, 1594, 1564, 1505, 1455, 1437, 1375, 1300, 1237, 1169, 1033, 957, 880, 854, 819, 733; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : 1.78 (6H, s, $(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 2.46 (1H, brs, OH), 7.50 (1H, d, J 4.5 Hz), 7.59–7.62 (1H, dd, J 1.2, 1.5 Hz), 7.95 (1H, s), 8.02 (1H, d, J 9.0 Hz), 8.25 (1H,

d, J 1.2 Hz), 9.06 (1H, d, J 4.5 Hz); HRMS calcd. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{13}\text{ClN}_4\text{O}$: 288.0778; found : 288.2278 (M^+), 290.2894 ($\text{M}+2$).

7-Chloro-4-(4-phenyl-[1,2,3]triazol-1-yl)-quinoline (7d) : IR (Film, cm^{-1}) : 3126, 1595, 1560, 1501, 1434, 1234, 1079, 1021, 953, 878, 820, 756, 693; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : 7.38–7.62 (5H, m), 7.93–7.96 (2H, m), 8.06 (1H, d, J 9.0 Hz), 8.25 (2H, s), 9.07 (1H, d, J 4.5 Hz); Anal. calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{11}\text{ClN}_4$: C, 66.56; H, 3.61; found : C, 66.11; H, 3.19.

4-(4-Bromomethyl-[1,2,3]triazol-1-yl)-7-chloro-quinoline (7e) : IR (Film, cm^{-1}) : 2924, 2845, 1590, 1562, 1436, 1073, 1040, 880, 817, 769; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : 5.00 (2H, s, CH_2Br), 7.50 (1H, d, J 4.5 Hz), 7.58–7.61 (1H, d, J 2.1, 1.8 Hz), 7.96–8.04 (2H, m), 8.25 (1H, d, J 1.8 Hz), 9.07 (1H, d, J 4.5 Hz); Anal. calcd. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_8\text{BrClN}_4$: C, 44.54; H, 2.49; found : C, 44.34; H, 2.59.

7-Chloro-4-(4-methoxymethyl-[1,2,3]triazol-1-yl)-quinoline (7f) : IR (Film, cm^{-1}) : 3132, 3080, 2925, 2815, 1612, 1561, 1504, 1455, 1437, 1382, 1235, 1189, 1119, 1099, 1046, 954, 878, 824; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : 3.53 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.84 (2H, s, OCH_2), 7.50 (1H, d, J 3.6 Hz), 7.60 (1H, d, J 9.0 Hz), 7.97–8.03 (2H, m), 8.24 (1H, s), 9.06 (1H, d, J 3.6 Hz); HRMS calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{11}\text{ClN}_4\text{O}$: 274.0621; found : 275.2818 ($\text{M}^+ + \text{H}$).

1-[1-(7-Chloro-quinolin-4-yl)-1H-[1,2,3]triazol-4-yl]-cyclohexanol (7g) : IR (Film, cm^{-1}) : 3353, 3150, 3057, 2926, 2849, 1612, 1597, 1564, 1455, 1439, 1262, 1229, 1156, 1031, 976, 882, 849, 808, 628; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : 1.68–1.83 (6H, m), 1.97–2.17 (4H, m), 2.69 (1H, brs, OH), 7.48–7.59 (2H, m), 7.96–8.02 (2H, m), 8.23 (1H, s), 9.03 (1H, d, J 4.2 Hz); HRMS calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{17}\text{ClN}_4\text{O}$: 328.1091; found : 329.2818 ($\text{M}^+ + \text{H}$).

7-Chloro-4-(4-phenoxyethyl-[1,2,3]triazol-1-yl)-quinoline (8a) : IR (Film, cm^{-1}) : 3069, 2930, 2875, 1598, 1494, 1456, 1439, 1302, 1240, 1034, 1015, 879, 821, 755, 692; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : 5.39 (2H, s, OCH_2), 7.00–7.06 (3H, m), 7.31–7.36 (2H, m), 7.50 (1H, d, J 4.5 Hz), 7.61 (1H, d, J 7.8 Hz), 7.96–7.99 (1H, s), 8.01 (1H, s), 8.25 (1H, s), 9.06 (1H, d, J 4.5 Hz); HRMS calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{13}\text{ClN}_4\text{O}$: 336.0778; found : 336.8967 (M^+).

7-Chloro-4-(4-o-tolyloxymethyl-[1,2,3]triazol-1-yl)-quinoline (8b) : IR (Film, cm^{-1}) : 3158, 3030, 2944, 2868, 1608, 1563, 1496, 1437, 1240, 1123, 1037, 1015, 955, 881, 824, 748; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : 2.27 (3H, s, CH_3), 5.40 (2H, s, OCH_2), 6.93 (1H, t, J 7.2 Hz), 7.02 (1H, d, J 8.4 Hz), 7.17–7.23 (2H, m), 7.51–7.63 (2H, m), 7.90 (1H, d, J 9.3 Hz), 8.06 (1H, s), 8.25 (1H, d, J 2.1 Hz), 9.08 (1H, d, J 4.8 Hz); HRMS calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{15}\text{ClN}_4\text{O}$: 350.0934; found : 350.2838 (M^+), 352.4694 ($\text{M}+2$).

7-Chloro-4-(4-m-tolyloxymethyl-[1,2,3]triazol-1-yl)-quinoline (8c) : IR (Film, cm^{-1}) : 3148, 3115, 3044, 2884, 1611, 1549, 1491, 1259, 1156, 1114, 1037, 1010, 819, 771; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : 2.35 (3H, s, CH_3), 5.34 (2H, s, OCH_2), 6.81–6.86 (3H, m), 7.20 (1H, t, J 7.5 Hz), 7.57–7.63 (2H, m), 8.01 (1H, d, J 9.3 Hz), 8.22 (1H, d, J 2.1 Hz), 8.28 (1H, s), 9.08 (1H, d, J 4.5 Hz); HRMS calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{15}\text{ClN}_4\text{O}$: 350.0934; found : 350.2838 (M^+).

7-Chloro-4-(4-p-tolyloxymethyl-[1,2,3]triazol-1-yl)-quinoline (8d) : IR (Film, cm^{-1}) : 3144, 3105, 2921, 1610, 1590, 1563, 1509, 1439, 1237, 1114, 1022, 955, 879, 814, 739; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : 2.31 (3H, s, CH_3), 5.35 (2H, s, OCH_2), 6.92–6.95 (2H, m), 7.11–7.14 (2H, m), 7.50 (1H, d, J 4.8 Hz), 7.58–7.62 (1H, dd, J 2.1, 2.1 Hz), 7.97 (1H, d, J 9.0 Hz), 8.08 (1H, s), 8.25 (1H, d, J 2.1 Hz), 9.06 (1H, d, J 4.8 Hz); HRMS calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{15}\text{ClN}_4\text{O}$: 350.0934; found : 350.2838 (M^+).

7-Chloro-4-(4-((4-chlorophenoxy)methyl)-1H-1,2,3-triazol-1-yl)quinoline (8e) : IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 2924, 2858, 1611, 1595, 1565, 1493, 1460, 1442, 1373, 1284, 1244, 1115, 1058, 1039, 1005, 957, 878, 817; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : 5.35 (2H, s, OCH_2), 6.95–7.01 (2H, m), 7.26–7.31 (2H, m), 7.50 (1H, d, J 4.8 Hz), 7.59–7.63 (1H, m), 7.94 (1H, d, J 9.0 Hz), 8.10 (1H, s), 8.25 (1H, d, J 2.1 Hz), 9.06 (1H, d, J 4.8 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl_3) : 61.90, 115.90, 115.96, 120.33, 124.32, 124.52, 126.33, 128.85, 129.33, 129.39, 136.77, 140.60, 144.55, 150.00, 151.23, 156.48; HRMS calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{12}\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_4\text{O}$: 370.0388; found : 371.0911 ($\text{M}^+ + \text{H}$).

7-Chloro-4-(4-((2,4-dichlorophenoxy)methyl)-1H-1,2,3-triazol-1-yl)quinoline (8f) : IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 2920, 2860, 1650, 1559, 1541, 1508, 1489, 1437, 1373, 1250, 1110,

1058, 1015, 957, 878, 748; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : 5.44 (2H, s, OCH_2), 7.45–7.50 (2H, m), 7.61 (1H, s), 7.79–8.00 (3H, m), 8.30 (1H, s), 9.00 (1H, s), 9.16 (1H, s); HRMS calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{11}\text{Cl}_3\text{N}_4\text{O}$: 403.9998; found : 404.9811 ($\text{M}^+ + \text{H}$).

7-Chloro-4-(4-((2,6-dichlorophenoxy)methyl)-1H-1,2,3-triazol-1-yl)quinoline (8g) : IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 2933, 1611, 1562, 1507, 1439, 1244, 1114, 1040, 1003, 879, 820, 782; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : 5.40 (2H, s, OCH_2), 7.04–7.10 (1H, t, J 9 Hz), 7.33–7.36 (2H, m), 7.53–7.63 (2H, m), 7.97–8.01 (2H, m), 8.24–8.27 (1H, d, J 3 Hz), 9.07 (1H, s); HRMS calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{11}\text{Cl}_3\text{N}_4\text{O}$: 403.9998; found : 404.9902 ($\text{M}^+ + \text{H}$).

7-Chloro-4-[4-(2-nitro-phenoxy)methyl]-[1,2,3]triazol-1-yl]quinoline (8h) : ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : 5.43 (2H, s, OCH_2), 6.68–7.14 (2H, m), 7.41–7.55 (3H, m), 7.90–8.10 (1H, m), 8.22–8.37 (2H, m), 8.43 (1H, s), 9.013–9.074 (1H, m); HRMS calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{12}\text{ClN}_5\text{O}_3$: 381.0629; found : 382.2853 ($\text{M}^+ + \text{H}$).

7-Chloro-4-[4-(4-nitro-phenoxy)methyl]-[1,2,3]triazol-1-yl]quinoline (8i) : IR (Film, cm^{-1}) : 2951, 2923, 1589, 1495, 1333, 1259, 1108, 1034, 1005, 878, 846, 820; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : 5.48 (2H, s, OCH_2), 7.18–7.21 (2H, m), 7.47 (1H, s), 7.59–7.65 (2H, m), 8.02 (1H, d, J 9.3 Hz), 8.24–8.27 (2H, m), 8.38 (1H, s), 9.10 (1H, d, J 4.5 Hz); HRMS calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{12}\text{ClN}_5\text{O}_3$: 381.0629; found : 382.2853 ($\text{M}^+ + \text{H}$).

7-Chloro-4-[4-(4-methyl-2-nitro-phenoxy)methyl]-[1,2,3]triazol-1-yl]quinoline (8j) : IR (Film, cm^{-1}) : 3057, 2923, 1612, 1553, 1531, 1502, 1354, 1263, 1229, 1036, 1009, 873, 810, 762; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : 2.37 (3H, s, CH_3), 5.49 (2H, s, OCH_2), 7.25–7.26 (1H, d, J 9.1 Hz), 7.38–7.42 (1H, dd, J 1.8, 1.8 Hz), 7.51–7.53 (1H, d, J 4.8 Hz), 7.59–7.63 (1H, dd, J 1.8, 2.1 Hz), 7.69 (1H, d, J 4.5 Hz), 7.96–7.99 (1H, d, J 9.1 Hz), 8.22–8.26 (2H, m), 9.08 (1H, d, J 4.5 Hz); HRMS calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{14}\text{ClN}_5\text{O}_3$: 395.0785; found : 395.5340 (M^+).

2-[1-(7-Chloro-quinolin-4-yl)-1H-[1,2,3]triazol-4-ylmethoxy]-benzaldehyde (8k) : IR (Film, cm^{-1}) : 2919, 2850, 1684, 1603, 1487, 1457, 1290, 1248, 1163, 1046, 832, 816, 758; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : 5.52 (2H, s, OCH_2), 7.13 (1H, t, J 7.2 Hz), 7.23 (1H, s), 7.53 (1H, d, J 4.5 Hz), 7.61–7.64 (2H, m), 7.87 (1H, d, J 7.5

Hz), 7.97 (1H, d, *J* 9.3 Hz), 8.17 (1H, s), 8.27 (1H, s), 9.09 (1H, d, *J* 4.2 Hz), 10.49 (1H, s, CHO); HRMS calcd. for C₁₉H₁₃ClN₄O₂ : 364.0727, found : 365.8860 (M⁺ + H).

4-[1-(7-Chloro-quinolin-4-yl)-1H-[1,2,3]triazol-4-ylmethoxy]-benzaldehyde (**8I**) : IR (Film, cm⁻¹) : 3162, 2832, 1687, 1591, 1508, 1431, 1305, 1262, 1161, 1035, 1005, 878, 821; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : 5.46 (2H, s, OCH₂), 7.16–7.19 (2H, m), 7.52 (1H, d, *J* 4.5 Hz), 7.61 (1H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz), 7.84–7.90 (2H, m), 7.98 (1H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz), 8.16 (1H, s), 8.26 (1H, s), 9.08 (1H, d, *J* 4.5 Hz), 9.19 (1H, s, CHO); ¹³C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl₃) : 61.92 (OCH₂), 115.02 (CH), 116.07 (CH), 120.50 (Cquart), 124.37 (CH), 124.70 (CH), 129.06 (CH), 129.59 (CH), 130.59 (Cquart), 132.07 (CH), 137.03 (Cquart), 140.72 (Cquart), 144.16 (Cquart), 150.19 (Cquart), 151.40 (CH), 162.85 (Cquart), 190.71 (CHO); HRMS calcd. for C₁₉H₁₃ClN₄O₂ : 364.0727; found : 365.8860 (M⁺ + H).

Assay for in vitro antimalarial activity and cytotoxicity :

The antimalarial activity was determined by measuring plasmodial LDH activity as described earlier²⁰. A suspension of red blood cells infected with D6 or W2 strain of *P. falciparum* (200 μL, with 2% parasitemia and 2% hematocrit in RPMI 1640 medium supplemented with 10% human serum and 60 μg/mL amikacin) was added to the wells of a 96-well plate containing 10 μL of serially diluted test samples. The plate was flushed with a gas mixture of 90% N₂, 5% O₂, and 5% CO₂ and incubated at 37 °C for 72 h in a modular incubation chamber (Billups-Rothenberg Inc., Del Mar, CA, USA). Parasitic LDH activity was determined according to the procedure of Makler and Hinrichs²¹. Briefly, 20 μL of the incubation mixture was mixed with 100 μL of the MalstatTM reagent (Flow Inc., Portland, OR, USA) and incubated at room temperature for 30 min. Twenty microliters of a 1 : 1 mixture of NBT/PES (Sigma, St Louis, MO, USA) was then added, and the plate is further incubated in the dark for 1 h. The reaction was then stopped by the addition of 100 μL of a 5% acetic acid solution. The plate was read at 650 nm. Artemisinin and chloroquine were included in each assay as antimalarial drug controls. IC₅₀

values were computed from the dose-response curves. To determine the selectivity index of antimalarial activity of compounds, their *in vitro* cytotoxicity to mammalian cells was also determined. The assay was performed in 96-well tissue culture-treated plates as described earlier²². Vero cells (monkey kidney fibroblasts) were seeded to the wells of 96-well plate at a density of 25000 cells/well and incubated for 24 h. Samples at different concentrations were added and plates were again incubated for 48 h. The number of viable cells was determined by Neutral Red assay. IC₅₀ values were obtained from dose-response curves. Doxorubicin was used as a positive control for cytotoxicity.

Acknowledgement

DSR thanks University Grants Commission (41-20282012(SR), 2012), New Delhi, India and DU-PURSE Grant, University of Delhi, Delhi, India for financial support. SM and HA are thankful to CSIR for the award of Junior and Senior Research Fellowship respectively.

References

1. E. Lallana, F. Fernandez-Trillo, A. Sousa-Herves, R. Riguera and E. Fernandez-Megia, *Pharm. Res.*, 2012, **29**, 902.
2. H. C. Kolb and K. B. Sharpless, *Drug Dis. Tod.*, 2003, **8**, 1128.
3. C. Petchprayoon, K. Suwanborirux, R. Miller, T. Sakata and G. Marriott, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 2005, **68**, 157.
4. R. Huisgen, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 357.
5. D. Wang, J. A. Sutcliffe, A. K. Oyelere, T. S. McConnell, J. A. Ippolito and J. N. Abelson, 2004, WO 2004029066.
6. X. Fu, C. Albermann, C. Zhang and J. S. Thorson, *Org. Lett.*, 2005, **7**, 1513.
7. J. P. Gil, *Pharmacogen*, 2008, **9**, 1385.
8. F. Loeb, W. M. Clark, G. R. Coateny, L. T. Coggeshall, F. R. Dieuaide, A. R. Dochez, E. G. Hankansson, E. K. Marshall (Jr.), C. S. Marvel, O. R. McCoy, J. J. Saper, W. H. Sebrell, J. A. Shannon and G. A. Carden (Jr.), *J. Am. Med. Assoc.*, 1946, **130**, 1069.
9. V. V. Kouznetsov and A. Gomez-Barrio, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2009, **44**, 3091.
10. R. J. Ridley, *Nature*, 2002, **415**, 686.
11. M. C. Murray and M. E. Perkins, *Annu. Rep. Med. Chem.*, 1996, **31**, 141.
12. S. Manohar, S. I. Khan and D. S. Rawat, *Chem. Biol. Drug Des.*, 2011, **78**, 124.
13. S. Manohar, S. I. Khan, S. K. Kandi, K. Raj, G. Sun, X. Yang, A. D. C. Molina, N. Ni, B. Wang and D. S.

- Rawat, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2013, **23**, 112.
14. S. Manohar, S. I. Khan and D. S. Rawat, *Chem. Biol. Drug Des.*, 2013, **81**, 625.
15. S. Manohar, U. C. Rajesh, S. I. Khan, B. L. Tekwani and D. S. Rawat, *ACS Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2012, **3**, 555.
16. N. Kumar, S. I. Khan, H. Atheaya, R. Mamgain and D. S. Rawat, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2011, **46**, 2816.
17. S. Manohar, S. I. Khan and D. S. Rawat, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2010, **20**, 322.
18. N. Kumar, S. I. Khan, M. Sharma, H. Atheaya and D. S. Rawat, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2009, **19**, 1675.
19. H. Atheaya, S. I. Khan, R. Mamgain and D. S. Rawat, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2008, **18**, 1446.
20. M. Jain, S. I. Khan, B. L. Tekwani, M. R. Jacob, S. Singh, P. P. Singh and R. Jain, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2005, **13**, 4458.
21. M. T. Makler and D. J. Hinrichs, *Am. J. Trop. Med. Hyg.*, 1993, **48**, 205.
22. J. Mustafa, S. I. Khan, G. Ma, L. A. Walker and I. A. Khan, *Lipids*, 2004, **39**, 167.